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2nd International Conference on
**Transforming Innovation in
Agriculture, Environment and
Health for Sustainable
Development**

TIAEHSD-2024

07th -08th September, 2024

**SOUVENIR
Cum ABSTRACT
Book**

Editors

Dr. Yogesh K. Agarwal

Dr. U. K. Singh

Dr. Hemant Kumar

Dr. Manish Kumar

Dr. Gaurav Agarwal

Co-Editors

Dr. Anil Kumar

Dr. Vipin Mishra

AgriLife 2024

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DISTRIBUTED AGROSENOUS PHYTONEMATODES IN THE AREAS AROUND THE LOWER ZARAFSHON RIVER**Kholisa Eshova and Candidate Dilafruz Yagmurova**

Department of Zoology, National University of Uzbekistan,

Email: eshova.kholisa@gmail.com: dilafruzayagmurova9722@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

The city of Bukhara, located in the lower reaches of the Zarafshan River, and its surrounding areas were very beautiful in ancient times - the world of animals and plants was unique, rich in lakes and running water, as the information in the work "History of Bukhara" by the historian Narshakhi confirms. According to its geographical location, Bukhara region belongs to the Central Asian dry continental climate province of the Turan subtropical climate region and is distinguished by its own characteristics belonging to the semi-desert region. The territory of Bukhara region consists of undulating, slightly sloping plains in the north-west with separate hills, the height of which is from 300 to 800 m above sea level. The water supply of the region is very uneven, a part of the Zarafshan river flows from the east of the region, forming small saline lakes in the lower part and disappearing in the sands. In the west, along the border of Turkmenistan, flows the Amudarya, whose waters are used to irrigate fields. The region's lakes consist of saline waters, the largest of which are Dengizkol, Ayakogitma, Shor, Karakyr, Hadicha. The general climatic conditions of the region are formed under the influence of desert climate and semi-desert climate. There are various negative stress effects in the production of agricultural products, one of which is phytonematodes. Although phytonematodes are microscopic worms, they cause billions of dollars in economic losses each year, and all crops worldwide are infested with at least one species of phytonematode parasite. In particular, according to the State Statistics Committee, in the Bukhara region in 2023 alone, more than 36 thousand 812 tons of corn, more than 249 thousand 118 tons of potatoes, 189 thousand 126 tons of tomatoes, 75 thousand 598 thousand 55 tons of cucumbers, 218 thousand 745 tons of grapes were harvested, more than 485 thousand 050 tons of grain were grown, onions - 211 thousand 289 tons. It is very important to study plant nematodes, which have a negative impact on the above-mentioned crops and are one of the factors that bring them into a stressful environment. The life of phytonematodes is associated with plants. Therefore, scientific studies of the relationships of phytonematodes with plants are important because they provide detailed information about the fauna and individual species of phytonematodes. The main goal of the research is to study and analyze the fauna and ecology of various phytonematodes of agrocenoses common in the Lower Zarafshan region.

Keywords: phytonematodes, fauna; agrocenosis; agriculture; parasite; soil; individ; type**USING HYPERSENSITIVITY REACTION PARAMETERS TO CHARACTERIZE COTTON GERMLASM SAMPLES FOR RESISTANCE TO THE VERTICILLUM WILT AGENT****Khotamov M.M., Rejapova M.M, Kurbanbaev I.D, Akhmedzhanov I.G.**

Institute of Genetics and Plant Experimental Biology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT

This report presents the results of an immunological study on the characteristics of individual disease resistance of various lines and samples of germplasm of the Cotton Gene Pool of the Institute of Genetics and Experimental Plant Biology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, numbering several thousand samples of *G. hirsutum* L. It is known that the criteria for

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